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The Becoming of a ‘Bride’: Compelling Circumstances and Complexities

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Abstract

Child marriage is a practice that oppresses and marginalises young women. In many obscure communities in India spread across different geographies, young women still do not have the language or space to address the violations inflicted on their bodies and minds simply because they are too young to even comprehend what child marriage does to them. What is worse is that the circumstances that push these women to such marriages and their plight are rarely discussed. The fact that child marriage exists in our society till today exposes how women are marginalized right from their childhood. The marginalities that child brides experience cannot be all generalised and looked at from a single lens as they deal with multiple layers of oppression simultaneously. In a lot of instances of child marriage, girls silently give in to their parents and male elders specifically, believing it to be their duty towards their parents and community. These young girls are bereft of any agency to express their wants and desires. This paper therefore tries to unpack the social realities that encumber upon a young girl thus forcing her to enter into matrimony much before she can comprehend the whole meaning of the word “marriage”. It also deals with the complexities of being a child bride.

Keywords: Child Marriage, Child Brides, Compelling Circumstances, Complexities

Introduction

Marriage is a milestone in human life which is celebrated across varied cultures and societies. It is an event which marks the union of not just two individuals but their families as well. However, when one is forced into this union, that too at an age when one is unable to decipher the complexities of marriage and the responsibilities that they entail, it may not remain such a joyous event. Within the institution of marriage, the roles allocated to the man and the woman differ from each other. The disparity between the roles assigned to men and women within a marital relationship are deeply rooted in patriarchy where the man performs his societal duties in the public sphere where on the other hand, the woman is performing her duties within

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the domestic space of the household, very often referred to as the private sphere. The concept of marriage that has been passed down through generations stresses on the idea of a woman's submission, acceptance and sacrifice. It is only when she subscribes to these norms that she is deemed womanly enough.

The interests of girl children and their perceptions are often overshadowed by quantitative impact of the phenomenon of child marriage. The child brides are never heard from first hand since the influence of the phenomenon are never looked at from their perspective. The patriarchal structures surround and trap women in specific domestic roles and therefore it becomes extremely difficult for them to escape the various complications they are exposed to on a regular basis. In such an extraordinarily complex web of poverty, patriarchal mindsets and control over sexuality, young girls are robbed of their childhood and most of the times; they do not even understand the implications that the practice has on their internal and external selves.

It thus becomes important to study and understand the compelling circumstances and complexities of the child brides since their lives are affected in multiple ways. Their movement towards adulthood is not just abrupt but also very dangerous both for their physical and emotional needs. The destruction of a childhood that results in a thrusting of forced adulthood needs to be looked at deeply for a better understanding of the lives of the child brides. Impact of these marriages on the lives of children and adolescents needs to be understood so that suitable interventions from the perspective of children are designed. More so, this needs to be done so from a feminist perspective as the need of the hour is gender equity and not just gender equality. According to the United Nations Gender equity talks about being fair to both men and women and equity leads to equality. Gender equality requires equal enjoyment by women and men of socially-valued goods, opportunities, resources and rewards.

Compelling Circumstances of Becoming a Child Bride

The problem of child marriage needs to be understood in terms of entrenched poverty and ignorance that sees the girl child as a burden, ingrained patriarchal mindsets, and the need to control their sexuality. Such marriages are often forced on young children due to poor understanding of the ills that accompany such a practice and a basic gender biased attitude of the parents as well as society. Few of the underlying circumstances that propel and compel them to be pushed into this evil are discussed below.

Poverty and Economic Instability

Poverty erodes the capacity of families to cope with the stress of sheltering growing girls especially if the girl is not studying or contributing to the family income. Girls are then seen as burdensome and illiteracy and large family size often compounds the problem of economic instability (Otoo, Naana&Pobi, 2003). Poverty and child marriage are intricately linked and where the parents consider marrying the young girl as a better choice that will ensure her protection. Presence of several girl children in the family and the fear of being able to find suitable matches for daughters continue to push such ignorant people into child marriage (Kaur, 2004). Extreme poverty often leads mothers to marry off daughters as children even when they themselves may have faced child marriage. This is emphasized to highlight how poor women despite knowing the traumas of having been a child bride push their girl children into this terrible grip of child marriage as circumstances are never favourable to take an alternative decision.

Due to the stigma attached to single women and the burden of dowry on poor families, parents find it right to marry their daughters as children as early as possible. Dowry is governed by strong patriarchal structures and norms. The dowry demands are higher for older girls so parent engages in child marriage to avoid the stress of paying high dowry. The demand for dowry in fact creates a burden on the family of the girls who are therefore inclined to marry the daughters during their childhood to reduce the dowry burden. Girl children are discriminated against due to negative feelings attached to dowry (Bose, 2012).

Lack of Education

Educational attainment remains a pipe dream for these young girls as with the onset of puberty, the first discussions in their families is about their marriage. Irrespective of whether they show interest in studies or not, protecting the family 'name' by not letting girls to be 'free' and 'uncontrolled' for a long time after menarche is a topmost priority in the families with adolescent girls. Besides this, knowing that the girls will leave them soon after marriage also invokes no interest in the parents to educate them as it is believed that their primary responsibilities are to look after the household (Chakarbarti, 1998; Gorney, 2011). In such a scenario, there are no possibilities of the girl having a scope of earning a livelihood. She will continue to be subsumed by the demands of domestic work and the demands of her husband, which eventually becomes a way of life for her.

Male Authority

Within the patriarchal context, marriage is considered to be compulsory since girls are considered burdensome and career choices and investment in girls' education are not priorities in their families. Women and girls are expected to be submissive and their roles within as well as outside the family are regulated by elders and traditional patriarchal norms which can only be ensured by marrying girls very young. It is believed that as they grow older they will tend to assert their freedom of choice which only the husband can and must control well in time. Decision making power is in the hands of the elder males who continue to further child marriages so as to control young women through obedience to patriarchal regulations. The mothers silently follow the patriarchal doctrines of getting the young girls married in their childhood thus playing their own submissive roles in furthering the patriarchal organization of the society (Santhya and Jeejeebhoy, 2007; Kalpagam, 2008).

Due to rigid patriarchal structures, these young married women are subjugated by the male stratum of the family where they are particularly vulnerable and unable to exercise any choice in their marital homes (Kalpagam, 2008). These married adolescents hardly have any say even in decisions related directly to their lives, or on their mobility and interaction with outsiders. Moreover, their behaviour is closely supervised by the elders of the family who are always ready to question their chastity. The existing societal patriarchal norms thus affect the lives of women through lack of agency and negotiating power because of the notion that it is mandatory for women to submit themselves to their husbands (Santhya and Jeejeebhoy, 2007).

Child Marriage, Bodies and the Idea of Sexuality

The young child brides have to traverse through very rough terrain in a world centred on patriarchy in the process of becoming a 'woman'. It begins with adolescence, which is a stage in life when individuals are developing a sense of self. This is the period when people understand their bodies and sexuality. In conservative communities where the idea of sexuality and love is not even remotely mentioned, it becomes all the more difficult for young women to comprehend the changes in their own bodies. Most of these marriages are not marriages of choice. In fact, the idea behind child marriage is to control a girl's sexuality before she becomes aware and begins to assert her agency over it (Mohlakoana, 2008). During this period of adolescence when they are forced into an institution that expects them to reproduce and treat their bodies and wombs just as a mechanical tool, there is nothing left to look forward to. They understand

the act of sex through unfounded experience because prior to that very experience of a sexual encounter with a man, nobody around her even mentions what the act entails. Thus there is a deep sense of fear attached to the idea of sexual intercourse because of unawareness. Their bodies become the site of both mental and physical violence, but that is the bargain they make to remain a 'good wife'.

Sexuality thus appears to be the contested ground on which child marriage is pivoted. Child brides do not raise a voice even if they are forced upon by their husbands, and if they raise their voice, they will have to bear the wrath of the entire community for even talking about their body. In fact, the idea of consent does not exist for them. When girls are pushed into child marriages, where they often experience forced and non-consensual physical and sexual encounters, it causes an irreparable damage to their sense of self.

Thus the above in short are a few of the imposing factors that continue to make child marriage a practice in our society. Patriarchy remains the unseen driving force behind this practice, fuelled by a society that has been strongly indoctrinated into these beliefs, norms and practices that always favour the male world. It can be observed that these factors continue to play upon each other. Poverty and ignorance, lack of education, male dominance and distorted ideas of sexuality continue to hound a young girl's life.

Complexities of the Problem of Child Marriage

Child marriage or forced marriage at a very tender age makes the young girls prone to various obstacles hampering their overall development. Young girls married as children are not matured enough to choose their life partners and understand what marriage is all about. Therefore, parents along with the other male members of the family look for prospective grooms on behalf of their daughters thereby affecting their future making them physically and mentally vulnerable to face the consequences of child marriage. Complexities in the form of losing their childhood, son preference and prioritizing marriage over education are discussed below.

Robbing their Childhood

By denying young girls their basic rights to the carefree life of a child and forcing them into marriage at a very early age, they are robbed of their childhood. Women's lives are always caught between the deeply entrenched web of patriarchal values, societal norms, culture, caste, class

and gender hierarchies that pervade in our society. A girl child's life is no different. Their childhoods are lost and aspirations crushed, encouraging the establishment of a society that views children as beings without an agency and basic human rights. Children are pushed to become brides which not just enhances their vulnerabilities, but also threatens the lives of the generations born out of those early marriages (Kundu et al., 2007). Yet, while getting married in childhood negatively impact girls and boys, it is girls who suffer the consequences way more than the boys.

Society provides the idea to these young women that her marital home is the only place where all their wishes and aspirations will come true. They are often told that all their aspirations of becoming a woman in the true sense of the word are going to be fulfilled by their husbands. Their mobility as young girls are restricted in their natal houses too with the assurance that the husband will do everything that they have dreamt of. Thus young girls are deprived of the gay abandon of childhood as their mobility and freedom is curtailed at every step lest society cast aspersions on their integrity and chastity. The same control continues to be exerted as she moves into her marital family, where the husband and in-laws then take over the reins of control.

Motherhood and Son-Preference

Becoming a mother for these young women also comes with a lot of anxieties and pressures. Motherhood for these child brides is immensely burdensome as they are forced to give the family a male child. It is the woman's responsibility to give the family an heir. Son preference in communities has been a pervasive practice for generations because the lineage is defined by men and not women. Property and land are only passed to men and thus there is pressure on women to produce sons instead of daughters (Kaur, 2008). The patriarchal control over property also gives them the power to economically dominate and control women's lives. They become decision makers in the private space because they are the bread winners. Thus, it is not surprising to see why women would be pressurised to produce a male child, even when reproduction is not in their control. When these young women step into their marital homes, they are told to give birth to a male child. Unfortunately for her, if she is unable to do so, she is cornered in many ways by people around her, sometimes even by telling her that she is not fortunate to become the mother of a male child. Parvathy (1999) is of the view that the moment a daughter is born, another kind of pressure begins to emerge upon her. The birth of a girl child makes her vulnerable to repeated pregnancies in the hope of a male child.

Thus, denying young girls their basic rights and forcing them into child marriage make them trapped in the deeply entrenched web of patriarchal values and societal norms that pervade in the Indian society. The innocence of childhood is lost in household responsibilities that follow child marriage without understanding the true meaning neither of marriage nor of family life and worse still impending motherhood at such a tender age.

Choice of Marriage over Education

There is pressure on young brides to conceive as soon as they are married. Forced out of education, young girls remain disempowered and dependent on the families of their in-laws. Most of these girls are overwhelmed with household work and do not get an opportunity to pursue education after marriage. They remain unskilled and economically and psychologically dependent on their husband and his family. The most important setback to girls because of child marriage is therefore their personal growth and education. Poor households prefer sending boys to school and keeping the girls home to assist parents in farms (Mathur et al., 2003). Marriage has been found to be a barrier to continuing education because of the expectation that girls should devote themselves to childbearing and household chores. Receiving formal education beyond higher secondary levels of education is found to delay the age at marriage. In households that are poor, girls are withdrawn from school to help with household work. Fear and concern regarding safety of girls while travelling to far away villages for school also prompts parents to withdraw them from school. The increase in responsibilities towards family after marriage greatly reduces the options of education for the young women.

According to the India Census (2011) around 84 million girl children covered under the Right to education Act dropped out of school. Thus girls' education is not valued; rather they are encouraged to groom themselves in traditional notions of femininity in household chores. Child brides are particularly vulnerable due to lower educational attainment resulting in lack of choice in choosing partners or husbands, greater restriction and lower autonomy in decision making.

Conclusion

The impact of child marriage is manifold. We have seen from the above discussions that poverty, lack of education and a patriarchal society continue to reinforce this dogmatic practice wherein these same set of factors emerge also as the consequences. Thus existing societal norms continue to tilt the scales in favour of men where women continue to face

the brunt in many forms. Illiteracy, forceful sex, economic dependencies are some of its consequences on the women.

It is thus girls who suffer the consequences with more intensity as their vulnerabilities in the marital homes are many. There are high levels of restrictions on them in their marital homes. The child brides are blamed for not producing male children or for repeated birth of female children or for not producing a baby in the first year of marriage. Such assertions no doubt affect the health of both mother and child, primarily owing to the poor physiological readiness of the young bride.

What is disturbing is that child marriage is also seen as a strategy to cope with high dowries and economic instability. Girls are perceived as burdens and little investment in their education and career is made. Families quickly opt for marriages especially when girls drop out of schools and marriage comes to be seen as a settlement. It is yet to be understood that the traditional beliefs of full womanhood are based on a false sense of security that marriage can provide to women. Even when there is awareness regarding the issue of child marriage within communities, there is a lack of sensitivity with respect to the implications the practice has on young people. These marriages are not marriages of choice. In fact, the idea behind child marriages is to control a girl's sexuality before she becomes aware and begin to assert her agency over it.

In conclusion, we can say that we need to develop a universal sensitive approach to the deep rooted problem of child marriages that has its roots not only in tradition and poverty but in continuing gender inequalities in the Indian society. It is also necessary to understand our responsibility of ensuring the rights of these young children and adolescents who are our future. The insecurities and fears should not prolong harmful traditions that deny children their human rights and crush their aspirations.

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